

Backbone and sidechain NMR assignments for the ribosome maturation factor RimP from *Escherichia coli*

Andreas Schedlbauer¹, Borja Ochoa-Lizarralde¹, Idoia Iturrioz¹, Retina Capuni¹, Tammo Diercks¹, Elisa de Astigarraga¹, Paola Fucini^{1,2,‡}, Sean R. Connell^{1,2, ‡},

¹Molecular Recognition and Host-Pathogen Interactions, CIC bioGUNE, Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Bizkaia, 48160 Derio, Bizkaia, Spain

²IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

‡Corresponding author E-mail address:

Sean R. Connell sean.connell@gmail.com, Paola Fucini pfucini@gmail.com.

Abstract

Ribosome biogenesis is an energetically expensive and complex cellular process that involves the coordinated folding of the ribosomal RNA and dozens of ribosomal proteins. It proceeds along multiple parallel pathways and is guided by trans-acting factors called ribosome assembly factors. Although this process has been studied for decades, there are still many open questions regarding the role of the ribosome assembly factors in directing the folding of ribosome biogenesis intermediates. RimP is one of the early acting factors and guides the assembly of the small 30S ribosomal subunit by facilitating the binding of ribosomal proteins uS5 and uS12. Here we report the virtually complete ¹H, ¹⁵N, and ¹³C chemical shift assignment of RimP from *Escherichia coli*. The NMR chemical shift data, deposited in the BMRB data bank under Accession No. 28014, indicates a widely folded protein composed of three *alpha* helices and eight *beta* strands.

Abbreviations

IPTG Isopropyl-thio- β -D-galactoside

E. coli *Escherichia coli*

RimP Ribosome maturation factor P

PIC Protease inhibitor cocktail

TCEP tris(2-carboxyethyl)-phosphine

RCI Random coil index

Keywords

NMR, ribosome maturation factors, rimP, Multidimensional NMR spectroscopy

Biological context

Bacterial ribosome assembly involves the coordinated and integrated folding of its ribosomal RNA (rRNA) along with diverse ribosomal r-protein components [Wilson & Nierhaus 2007] [Shajani,Sykes & Williamson 2011] [Davis & Williamson 2017]. Concurrent with this folding, the rRNA is processed (i.e. trimmed from a larger transcript) while both rRNA and r-proteins are modified post-transcriptionally and –translationally, respectively. This assembly process

is guided by a growing number of known assembly factors that include GTPases, modification enzymes (e.g. methylases), helicases, and other chaperones. Although their specific molecular roles are not generally established, these assembly factors are believed to facilitate ribosome assembly by directing r-protein binding to the rRNA and guiding rRNA folding by avoiding kinetic traps, which are alternative RNA conformations that slowly refold to the native structure and derive from a degeneracy of local interactions [Woodson 2000] .

The assembly factor RimP was first identified from the observation that a *rimP* chromosomal deletion reduced the amount of both translating 70S ribosomes and accumulated free 30S relative to 50S subunits [Nord,Bylund,Lövgren & Wikström 2009]. Importantly, the free 30S showed characteristics of immature subunits as they contained 17S precursor rather than mature 16S rRNA. Taken together, these observations indicated that *rimP* deletion leads to deficient 30S biogenesis. A role of RimP in 30S assembly was further confirmed by *in vitro* 30S reconstitution experiments, where RimP accelerated the binding of r-proteins uS5 (by a factor of 2) and uS12 (by a factor of 6) [Bunner et al. 2010]. Both are among the last r-proteins that bind to the assembling 30S subunit [Mizushima & Nomura 1970] and it was, therefore, postulated that RimP likewise acts during the late stages of 30S biogenesis [Bunner,Nord,Wikström & Williamson 2010]. The role of RimP in uS5 and uS12 binding to 30S subunit was also demonstrated *in vivo*, by showing that both r-proteins were depleted in ribosome assembly intermediates isolated from a *rimP* deletion strain [Sashital,Greeman & Williamson 2014]. Moreover, as formation of the central *pseudoknot* (a 16S rRNA element contacted by uS5 and uS12) was impaired in these intermediates, the authors suggested that RimP is among the first late stage assembly factors acting on the assembling 30S subunit and, thus, assisting in a stabilization of the central *pseudoknot* to facilitate uS5 and uS12 binding. A direct interaction of RimP with uS5 and uS12 had already been suggested by interaction network studies in *E. coli* [Butland et al. 2005] while, in *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, an interaction with uS12 was shown by co-immunoprecipitation and tandem affinity purification [Chu et al. 2018]. The importance of RimP for cellular function is highlighted by the fact that its deletion in *E. coli* leads to growth defects while its homologs SP14.3 and MSMEG_2624 in *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, respectively, are essential for viability [Chu et al. 2018] [Yu et al. 2001]. Moreover, RimP is essential for the survival of *Mycobacterium fortuitum* under acidic *in vitro* conditions mimicking the lower pH inside macrophages [Poonam,Yennamalli,Bisht & Shrivastava 2019] and was shown to be critical for *in vitro* *Salmonella enteritidis* virulence assays [Chang,Pang,He & Kwang 2008] .

The high resolution structures of RimP homologs SP14.3 from *Streptococcus pneumoniae* [Yu et al. 2001] and MSMEG_2624 from *Mycobacterium smegmatis* [Chu et al. 2018] are very similar and feature two domains, where the N-terminal domain resembles ribosomal protein S3 and the C-terminal domain shows a *sm*-fold [Chu et al. 2018] [Yu et al. 2001]. Yet, both RimP homolog structures differ in their interdomain arrangement [Chu et al. 2018] and by an additional α -helix at the C-terminus of MSMEG_2624. We have, therefore, complemented these studies by determining a solution structure for RimP from *E. coli*, which shares 16% sequence identity with its homologues from both *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Mycobacterium smegmatis*.

Here we report the ^1H , ^{15}N , and ^{13}C NMR chemical shift assignment and derived secondary structure for RimP from *E. coli*. All NMR assignment data has been deposited in the BMRB data bank under Accession No. 28014.

Methods and experiments

RimP expression and purification

The DNA encoding *E. coli* ribosome maturation factor P (RimP) (Uniprot P0A8A8) was inserted into p7XNH3 vector [Geertsma & Dutzler 2011] by inserting the gene downstream of a tag sequence encoding 10 histidine residues followed by a HRV 3C Protease cleavage site and a single serine linker (MHHHHHHHHHHHLEVLFGGPS-). The plasmid was then transformed into *E. coli* strain BL21 (DE3) for overexpression. Cells were grown in [U-¹³C, ¹⁵N] enriched M9 media to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.6 prior to induction with IPTG (0.5 mM) for 36h at 18°C and were then harvested by centrifugation for 30 min at 5000 rpm (rotor 8.100). The resulting pellet was resuspended in lysis buffer (100 mM Tris pH 8, 1M NaCl, 10% Glycerol, 100µM TCEP, 0.5% TritonX-100 plus one tablet of cComplete EDTA-free PIC (Roche)) and lysed by sonication.

The lysate was then incubated with 10 µl benzonase (20 U/µl) per 40 ml for 45 min at room temperature and subsequently cleared by centrifugation at 42000 × g_{ave} at 4°C for one hour. The resulting supernatant was passed through 0.45 µm and 0.22 µm syringe filters prior to loading on a 5ml HisTrap affinity column pre-equilibrated with loading Buffer A (50 mM Tris.HCl pH 7.8, 300 mM NaCl, 50µM TCEP, 10% glycerol) at 0.5 ml/min flow rate. After washing the column (to removed weakly bound contaminants) with 10 column volumes of Buffer A plus 2% Buffer B (50 mM Tris.HCl pH 7.8, 300 mM NaCl, 500 mM Imidazole, 50 µM TCEP, 10% glycerol), the protein was eluted in one step by applying 45% buffer B (225 mM imidazole). RimP containing fractions were passed through a HiPrep™ 26/10 desalting column equilibrated with Buffer A to remove imidazole from the sample prior to digestion with 3C protease for cleaving the N-terminal His-tag. After injection onto a Superdex 75/16/600 prep grade column connected with an inline 5ml HisTrap column (to remove 3C protease and undigested protein) equilibrated with 10 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 6 mM MgCl₂, 150 mM NH₄Cl, 75 µM TCEP), the sample was concentrated in a VIVA spin 10 ml concentrator (5K cutoff, Amicon). The purity of the obtained RimP protein was assessed by 12% SDS-PAGE and MALDI TOF mass spectroscopy.

NMR spectroscopy

After exchanging purified RimP to NMR buffer (10 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 6 mM MgCl₂, 150 mM NH₄Cl, 75 µM TCEP, and 7% D₂O or 100% D₂O), the sample was concentrated to 900 µM in a VIVA spin 10 ml concentrator, centrifuged to remove any precipitate, and transferred into a 5 mm NMR Shigemi tube. All NMR experiments were recorded at 298 K. A suite of complementary 3D HNCO, HN(CA)CO, HNCA, HN(CO)CA, HNCACB, HN(CO)CACB, HN(CA)HA, and HN(COCA)HA BEST-TROSY experiments for sequential backbone assignment plus 3D (H)C,CH-, H,NH- and (H)C,NH-edited NOESY experiments (all with 150 ms mixing time) for structure analysis were recorded on a 800 MHz BRUKER AVANCE III spectrometer (equipped with a 5mm TCI cryoprobe). A 2D constant time ¹³C HSQC and 3D (H)CCH-TOCSY experiment for sidechain assignment were recorded on a 600MHz BRUKER AVANCE III spectrometer (equipped with a 5 mm TXI probe) using the sample dissolved in 100% D₂O. ¹H chemical shifts were directly referenced to added DSS (2,2-dimethyl-2-silapentane-5-sulphonic acid); ¹³C and ¹⁵N chemical shifts were then referenced indirectly to ¹H according to IUPAC ratios (http://www.bmrwisc.edu/ref_info/cshift.shtml).

All NMR data was processed with NMRpipe [Delaglio, Grzesiek, Vuister, Zhu, Pfeifer & Bax 1995] and analysed with CcpNmr [Skinner, Fogh, Boucher, Ragan, Mureddu & Vuister 2016]. The secondary structure of RimP was predicted with TALOS+ [Shen, Delaglio, Cornilescu & Bax 2009] .

NMR Assignment, secondary structure prediction, and NMR data deposition

The ^{15}N TROSY spectrum (Figure 1) of *E. coli* RimP (16.7 kDa, 151 residues) shows sharp backbone amide correlation signals of rather uniform intensities for all but the 5 proline residues along with a large chemical shift dispersion typical for well folded proteins with prevailing β -sheet structure. The backbone (including CB) signals for 138 (94.5%) of the 146 non-proline residues could be assigned; the amide signals of residues M1 to L4, R32, E43, T69, and F86 were undetectable presumably due to strong line broadening from conformational exchange processes. Sidechain chemical shifts could be assigned for 148 residues (98%), including all prolines except P84 (where assignment is incomplete).

Regular secondary structure elements in RimP (Figure 2) were predicted from all backbone chemical shifts (CO, CA, CB, N, HN, HA) using TALOS+ [Shen et al. 2009] and were corroborated by observed HN-HN' and HN-HA' NOE patterns. Thus, eight β strands (β 1: 21-30, β 2:34-41, β 3:72-78 , β 4:97-103, β 5:113-120, β 6:124-129, β 7:132-137, β 8:142-147) and three α -helices (α 1:4-18, α 2:48-64, α 3:88-94) were identified with consistently high order parameters ($S^2 > 0.8$) and in the sequential order α 1- β 1- β 2- α 2- β 3- α 3- β 4- β 5- β 6- β 7- β 8.

The chemical shift values for the ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{15}N resonances of RimP have been deposited in the BioMagResBank (<http://www.bmrwisc.edu/>) under accession number 28014.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by grants from the European Union's Seventh Framework Program (Marie Curie Actions; COFUND; to S.R.C. and A.S.), Marie Curie Action Career Integration Grant (PCIG14-GA-2013-632072 to P.F.), and Ministerio de Economía Y Competitividad Grant (MINECO, CTQ2017-82222-R to P.F., S.R.C.). We thank MINECO for the Severo Ochoa Excellence Accreditation (SEV-2016-0644) and the proteomics platform of CICbiogune for sample analysis by MALDI TOF mass spectroscopy. This is a pre-print of an article published in *Biomolecular NMR Assignments*. The final authenticated version is available online at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12104-020-09943-w>.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- Bunner, A. E.; Nord, S.; Wikström, P. M. and Williamson, J. R. (2010).** *The effect of ribosome assembly cofactors on in vitro 30S subunit reconstitution.*, Journal of molecular biology 398: 1-7.
- Butland, G.; Peregrín-Alvarez, J. M.; Li, J.; Yang, W.; Yang, X.; Canadien, V.; Starostine, A.; Richards, D.; Beattie, B.; Krogan, N.; Davey, M.; Parkinson, J.; Greenblatt, J. and Emili, A. (2005).** *Interaction network containing conserved and essential protein complexes in Escherichia coli.*, Nature 433: 531-537.
- Chang, J.; Pang, E.; He, H. and Kwang, J. (2008).** *Identification of novel attenuated Salmonella Enteritidis mutants.*, FEMS immunology and medical microbiology 53: 26-34.
- Chu, T.; Weng, X.; Law, C. O. K.; Kong, H.-K.; Lau, J.; Li, S.; Pham, H. Q.; Wang, R.; Zhang, L.; Kao, R. Y. T.; Lau, K.-F.; Ngo, J. C. K. and Lau, T. C. K. (2018).** *The ribosomal maturation factor P from Mycobacterium smegmatis facilitates the ribosomal biogenesis by binding to the small ribosomal protein S12.*, The Journal of biological chemistry 294: 372-378.
- Davis, J. H. and Williamson, J. R. (2017).** *Structure and dynamics of bacterial ribosome biogenesis.*, Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences 372.
- Delaglio, F.; Grzesiek, S.; Vuister, G. W.; Zhu, G.; Pfeifer, J. and Bax, A. (1995).** *NMRPipe: a multidimensional spectral processing system based on UNIX pipes.*, Journal of biomolecular NMR 6: 277-293.
- Geertsma, E. R. and Dutzler, R. (2011).** *A versatile and efficient high-throughput cloning tool for structural biology.*, Biochemistry 50: 3272-3278.
- Mizushima, S. and Nomura, M. (1970).** *Assembly mapping of 30S ribosomal proteins from E. coli.*, Nature 226: 1214.
- Nord, S.; Bylund, G. O.; Lövgren, J. M. and Wikström, P. M. (2009).** *The RimP protein is important for maturation of the 30S ribosomal subunit.*, Journal of molecular biology 386: 742-753.
- Poonam; Yennamalli, R. M.; Bisht, G. S. and Shrivastava, R. (2019).** *Ribosomal maturation factor (RimP) is essential for survival of nontuberculous mycobacteria Mycobacterium fortuitum under in vitro acidic stress conditions.*, 3 Biotech 9: 127.
- Sashital, D.; Greeman, C. and Williamson, J. (2014).** *A combined quantitative mass spectrometry and electron microscopy analysis of ribosomal 30S subunit assembly in E. coli.*, eLife 3: 1-26.
- Shajani, Z.; Sykes, M. T. and Williamson, J. R. (2011).** *Assembly of bacterial ribosomes.*, Annual review of biochemistry 80: 501-526.
- Shen, Y.; Delaglio, F.; Cornilescu, G. and Bax, A. (2009).** *TALOS+: a hybrid method for predicting protein backbone torsion angles from NMR chemical shifts.*, Journal of biomolecular NMR 44: 213-223.
- Skinner, S. P.; Fogh, R. H.; Boucher, W.; Ragan, T. J.; Mureddu, L. G. and Vuister, G. W. (2016).** *CcpNmr AnalysisAssign: a flexible platform for integrated NMR analysis.*, Journal of biomolecular NMR 66: 111-124.
- Wilson, D. N. and Nierhaus, K. H. (2007).** *The weird and wonderful world of bacterial ribosome regulation.*, Critical reviews in biochemistry and molecular biology 42: 187-219.
- Woodson, S. (2000).** *Recent insights on RNA folding mechanisms from catalytic RNA.*, Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences CMLS 57: 796-808.

Yu, L.; Gunasekera, A. H.; Mack, J.; Olejniczak, E. T.; Chovan, L. E.; Ruan, X.; Towne, D. L.; Lerner, C. G. and Fesik, S. W. (2001). *Solution structure and function of a conserved protein SP14. 3 encoded by an essential Streptococcus pneumoniae gene.*, Journal of molecular biology 311: 593-604.

Figure 1. 2D ^{15}N TROSY spectra of uniformly $^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}$ labeled RimP (in 10 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 6mM MgCl_2 , 150 mM NH_4Cl , 75 μM TCEP, 7% D_2O), acquired at 298K on a 800 MHz BRUKER AVANCE III spectrometer. Aliased signals (in F1) are colored blue. Resonance assignments have been deposited in the BioMagResBank (<http://www.bmrb.wisc.edu/>) under accession number 28014. Note that residual -NHD correlations (max. 7%, from Asn and Gln sidechains) are suppressed below the minimal contour level by the NH_1 multiplicity filter implicit in the ST2-PT module of the TROSY experiment.

Figure 2. (Top) Regular secondary structure propensity in RimP (red = α -helix, green = β -strand), as predicted by TALOS+ from the complete set of backbone chemical shifts (CO, CA, CB, N, HN, HA) for 138 residues. (Bottom) Pertaining order parameters, S^2 .